

'The Small Castles by the Marshy Shore'

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Summary

In mid-2021 a series of earthworks were identified on LiDAR which appeared to be the remains of a previously unrecorded archaeological settlement. This abstract contains a summary of archaeological research as part of a master's by Research degree with Manchester Metropolitan University, using multimodal approaches (including map regression analysis, LiDAR and archival research) as well as practical archaeological techniques to identify a site of potential archaeological interest in Llangwyllog, Anglesey, North Wales.

KEYWORDS: mapping, LiDAR, archaeology, landscape, research

1. Introduction

Figure 1: LiDAR of earthworks near Glan Gors, Llangwyllog.

1.1 The genesis of this work began with the discovery of earthwork features at farmland *near Glan Gors*, within the parish of Llangwyllog, Anglesey, an island found in the northwest of Wales. The features initially identified suggested the presence of a previously unrecorded defended settlement site in the area, built on a substantial scale.

1.2 Correspondence with Dr Ben Edwards of Manchester Metropolitan university, and Andrew Davidson of Gwynedd Archaeological Trust, support these initial suspicions, with the suggestion that it may be late prehistoric to Roman in date. This was further supported with the discovery of Roman period artefacts in the nearby parish of Coedana, hinting at previously unrecorded settlement in the region.

2. Methodology

2.1 Prior to any practical work carried out on the site, a thorough Desk Based Assessment would have to be carried out. This would prove invaluable as to establishing any potential archaeological context for the site within the existing landscape.

2.2 To this end, the use of digital mapping resources such as Digimap's Historic Ordnance Survey collection and LiDAR data would prove invaluable assets, along with digitised archival assets (including aerial photography and additional mapping data) from the Welsh Government, National Library of Wales, British Museum and Cambridge University. The use of techniques such as 'map regression analysis' are useful in determining the age of a site, as well as its presence within the local landscape.

3. Site history

Figure 2: Section from Robert Dawson's 'Holyhead' map, c. 1818.

3.1 The earliest mapping data for the area is Robert Dawson's Holyhead map, produced in 1818 as one of the earliest Ordnance maps of the area. Dawson (1771-1860) was an English born surveyor with a keen eye for detail and appeared to express an interest in archaeological features within the landscape, which he would mark with a Gothic text.

3.2 Yet the earthworks at the Llangwyllog site are not marked on this early map (See Figure 2). This may be due to their distance from the main road, seemingly as Dawson is keen to reference sites near roads or trackways. These included references to a standing stone in a field near *Hafod* farm to the west of the site (see Figure 2), as well as references to a fortified enclosure near *Gwyndy Quarry*.

3.3 Later OS maps (1889 onwards) also contained no references to this site, a puzzling observation given its scale and prominence within the landscape. Its possible that its low-lying location obstructed view from the road which, combined with little archaeological investigation into the area, helped ensure its secrecy.

3.5 Tenancy records relating to *Bryn Golau* farm, a tenancy farm owned by Trescawen Hall among other landowners, revealed a series of interesting fieldnames on lands near *Glan Gors*, including references to a *Cestyll Byron* or 'small castles' (WD6/122, LLE/239) and 'Llomiau yn y Cestyll' or 'earthworks of the castles' (WD6/117). Although no map was produced for this document, by using other field names in the document (such as *Cae Bodwin*), as well as historical mapping evidence, we could confidently place the approximate location of both names as being near or at the earthworks near *Glan Gors*.

3.6 It is clear from a study of the archaeological record within 3km of the study area that the landscape has seen occupation for thousands of years. The discovery of worked flints (lithics) at fields in Coedana suggest that people were at least visiting the area during the Mesolithic, at least 8,000 years ago (see Figure 2).

Figure 3: Mesolithic flints from study area.

3.8 By the Bronze Age, the landscape appeared to be a focus for high profile settlement and ritual activity. A hoard of metal objects and beads including those of amber, a rare material in Wales, was recorded west of Llangwyllog parish church (Lynch 1991; p. 245). The discovery of two stone 'battle axes' from *Maen Gwyn* in Coedana hinted at high status contacts from parts of Scotland and Ireland (1991; p. 140).

3.9 Evidence of potential burial sites such as barrows (mounds of earth containing cremated or inhumation burials) are reported within the landscape, further hinting the importance of the landscape as both an area to settle as well as to be buried within.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 With this background information in place, we can utilise practical archaeological techniques, consisting of a study of LiDAR data, aerial photography, and practical fieldwork to help further understand this site. In terms of practical fieldwork artefact retrieval exercises such as metal detecting and fieldwalking surveys, as well as prospective methods such as geophysical survey utilising both magnetometry and ground penetrating radar surveys.

4.2 Of particular interest was the study of a potential unrecorded route or trackway running west of the study area. A metalled road surface was identified immediately west of the earthworks, which may have aligned with a 2.5km trackway further north. By following hedgerows and extant trackways in the landscape, using both historical and current Ordnance Survey maps, it is possible to propose the direction of a previously unrecorded routeway, which seemingly interacts to a proposed Roman road network in Central Anglesey (Hopewell 2013). Although only excavation can definitively prove this, the presence of Roman period findspots near this proposed routeway is comparable to those found at other routeways nearby (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Proposed Roman routeways in study area, with purple line newly proposed route.

4.3 Aerial photography of the Anglesey landscape, carried out in 1944-5, shows the extant earthworks, showing how little of the site has changed. Satellite imagery carried out by Google in the summer of 2006 also highlighted cropmarks indicative of potential archaeology on the site. An image from Cambridge University Collection of Aerial Photography (CUCAP), taken in 1982, showed rectilinear, linear, and curvilinear cropmarks nearby indicative of possible trackways, settlement, and associated enclosures within the immediate landscape of *Glan Gors* (RC8ET072).

4.4 This new data, coupled with LiDAR analysis proved useful in further defining the potential archaeology of this landscape, and has proven a very powerful and successful tool for archaeological prospection (Chase et. al. 2017). In this instance, airborne LiDAR revealed a complex presence of earthworks in the landscape -not only the large, rectilinear enclosure at *Glan Gors*, but of other defended enclosures further south. Of these however the example at *Glan Gors* is the largest, measuring 400m wide by over 570m long. When compared to other defended sites on Anglesey, the *Cestyll Byrion* site may be considered one of the largest currently recorded on the island.

Figure 5: Interpretation of LiDAR features at Glan Gors.

4.5 To aid in further interpretation of the potential archaeology at this site, geophysical survey was conducted to help determine the age and function of this site using a gradiometer (or magnetometer). These sensitive pieces of geophysical survey equipment detect concentrations of iron particles in the ground (which make up 6% of soil). Depending on the concentration and distribution of these particles, these can be used to identify pits, ditches and even structures within the landscape. These are later run through specialist software such as Geoplot to plot the data visually to aid with interpretation and analysis.

4.6 Over half of the site, totalling 79 30m by 30m grids, have currently been surveyed. These identified numerous anomalies suggestive of potential archaeology under the ground (see Figure 6). These include evidence of possible 'roundhouses' (a type of prehistoric house); rectilinear and curvilinear enclosures (possibly animal pens or ritual enclosures); trackways, pit groups, postholes (some arranged into linears) and stone structures/features. These anomalies were found both inside and outside the earthworks, which reinforce the point of wider archaeology within the study area. Furthermore, a series of strong linear magnetic anomalies on its western bank suggest it may have once been stone faced, which may have served both a practical function as well as a status marker in the landscape.

4.7 Current interpretations of the anomalies suggest that we are looking at a large, late prehistoric defended settlement. Its location on an area of lowland and its close proximity both to the local river Cefni and an area of marsh, is characteristic of late Iron Age settlement sites in Britain, with comparable sites such as *Caer Leb* near Brynsiencyn, also on Anglesey (Waddington 2013, p. 147).

Figure 6: Geophysical survey results of 'Cestyll Byrion' site.

5.2 Conclusion

5.1 In conclusion, current research of this site and study area have shown the importance of multimodal methods when studying any previously unrecorded archaeological landscapes. In many instances, mapping data can be used to track lost routeways and trackways in the landscape, hinting at a past far more connected than previously thought.

5.2 Where mapping data for certain archaeological sites may be lacking, new digital methods of investigation such as LiDAR can be utilised to great success as shown in this study.

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